

Supporting Information

Direct electrocaloric characterization of polyvinylidene fluoride-based co- and terpolymers over a wide temperature range

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Contents:

S1.) Fabrication of polymer films	2
S2.) Film thickness determination.....	4
S3.) Differential scanning calorimetry of polymer powders	5
S4.) Dielectric spectroscopy of films	9
S5.) Room-temperature bipolar polarization–electric field loops	13
S6.) Temperature dependent polarization data	15
S7.) Comparison of 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymers.....	19
S8.) Direct electrocaloric measurements with infrared camera	22
S9.) Specific heat capacity of polymer powders	30
S10.) Finite element modeling	32
S11.) Indirect electrocaloric measurements – Landau phenomenological approach.....	35
S12.) Electrocaloric measurements of polymer films - comparison with the literature.....	37
References.....	42

S1.) Fabrication of polymer films

Five different 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30\text{--}0.55$) copolymer powders, i.e., 30TrFE (lot no. 62-111), 35TrFE (lot no. 62-031), 45TrFE (lot no. 62-145), 50TrFE (lot no. 52-063) and 55TrFE (lot no. 52-054), two 100xTrFE-100yCFE terpolymer powders, i.e., 32TrFE-8CFE (lot no. 64-014) and 31TrFE-7CFE (lot no. 64-018), and one 100xTrFE-100yCTFE terpolymer powder, i.e., 28TrFE-7CTFE (lot no. 53-075), were provided by Arkema-Piezotech, France. The ratios between the different monomers and their exact amount in each composition are shown in Fig. S1. Note that these ratios represent an average composition of the entire batch produced by the manufacturer, while the exact composition of the prepared films may vary slightly.

Figure S1. Investigated compositions of PVDF-based copolymers and terpolymers with defined quantities of the individual monomer units.

Different steps of sample processing are shown in Fig. S2. To prepare free-standing polymer films, PVDF-based powders (Figs. S1 and S2a) were dissolved in 2-butanone ($\geq 99.0\%$, Sigma-Aldrich) by mixing them at room temperature for 12 h to obtain a 10 wt.% solution (Fig. S2b). The prepared PVDF-based solution was filtered with 5 μm PTFE filters (Whatman ReZist). The PVDF-based solution was then applied to a clean glass substrate (A4 format), where uniform films were formed using the doctor blade coating technique (TQC Sheen, The Netherlands, Fig. S2c). The width of the used doctor blade was 150 mm, while the thickness of the wet film was adjusted to (300 ± 25) μm . The blade-coated films were dried at room temperature for 0.5 h and then crystallized in a chamber furnace (Binder FD 56, Germany, Fig. S2d). To ensure high crystallinity of the samples, the prepared films were annealed at a temperature of 10–20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ below the melting point of the polymers. According to the results of differential scanning calorimetry of powders (Section S3), two different annealing conditions were chosen. All TrFE-based copolymer films were annealed at 140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h, while all CFE- and CTFE-based terpolymer films were annealed at 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 h. After crystallization, the annealed polymer films (Fig. S2e) were removed from the glass substrate by immersion in deionized water and subsequent drying at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight (Binder FD 56, Germany) to obtain free-standing films (Fig. S2f).

For electrical characterization, ~ 100 nm thick Au electrodes were deposited through a shadow mask using a planar magnetron sputtering system (Bal-Tec, MED 020). The choice of Au as electrode material was crucial to obtain reliable and repeatable results, especially when electric fields above $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ were applied. Although Au is one of the most ductile metals, it has been shown to retain good electrical conductivity even when stretched by more than 10% of the tensile strain.¹ In contrast, problems with cracks in the electrodes occurred when Pt electrodes were used. Round electrodes with a diameter of 4–6 mm were used for all electrical characterizations (Fig. S2g). After sputtering of the electrodes on both sides of the films, the samples were cut into individual metal-insulator-metal (MIM)-structured capacitors (Fig. S2h). To gain access to the upper and lower electrodes, Cu wires (diameter 0.1 mm, Block, Germany) were bonded with silver epoxy (RS PRO), as shown in Fig. S2j. For direct measurements of the electrocaloric effect with an infrared camera, additional black ink was optionally applied to increase the emissivity of the sample surface (Fig. S2i and S2k). Further details can be found in the Materials and Methods section of the manuscript and in Ref. [2].

Figure S2. Photographs of the different steps of sample processing.

S2.) Film thickness determination

Knowing the exact thickness of the prepared samples is essential for accurate electrical measurements and for reliable comparison of the electrical characterization results of different compositions. The film thickness was verified from cross-sections using optical microscopy. The electroded samples were precisely sectioned with a cryo-ultramicrotome (EM UC6, Leica Microsystems), resulting in a typical thickness range of 8 μm to 12 μm for all investigated samples (Fig. S3). In addition, the thickness of the printed black ink layers used for direct characterization of the electrocaloric effect was found to be between 3 μm and 4 μm on average (Fig. S3).

Figure S3. Examples of optical microscope images of cut cross-sections of various copolymer and terpolymer samples. In addition to the thickness of the active (electroded) part of the samples, the thickness of the printed black ink layers was also measured. The photographs on the left show where the samples were sliced.

S3.) Differential scanning calorimetry of polymer powders

The thermal changes corresponding to the structural phase transitions (i.e., melting, crystallization and ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transitions) of the polymers were investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC 3+, Mettler Toledo, Switzerland). The measurements were performed on as-received PVDF-based powders (10–12 mg) placed in standard 20 μL Al crucibles with lids. To minimize instrumental errors, a blank measurement of empty crucible with lid was subtracted from all sample measurements. Two consecutive heating and cooling cycles were performed for each composition to exclude the possible imprint from the powder processing. In the first cycle, the samples were heated from 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (first heating) and then cooled to 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (first cooling). The samples were then heated again to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (second heating) and then cooled back to 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (second cooling). Heating and cooling rates of 5 K min^{-1} were used for all measurements.

The temperature dependence of the DSC signals for all 100 x TrFE-based copolymers ($x = 0.30\text{--}0.55$) from the second heating and cooling run is shown in Fig. S4. The ferroelectric-to-paraelectric phase transitions of all copolymers, also called Curie temperatures, appear as endothermic peaks in the heating curves in Fig. S4b. The Curie temperature (T_C) decreases with increasing TrFE co-monomer content, from 103 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30TrFE to 58 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 55TrFE composition (Figs. S4b and S5a). On the other hand, the Curie temperature on cooling is almost independent of TrFE content and stabilizes at ~ 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figs. S4e and S5a). Several peaks in TrFE-poor compositions (30TrFE and 35TrFE) may result from the coexistence of multiple phases or polymer conformations with slight compositional variations. Both the decrease in T_C upon heating and the stability of the paraelectric phase upon cooling are consistent with previous studies.³⁻⁷ The large discrepancy between heating and cooling runs, also called thermal hysteresis, in TrFE-poor compositions ($\leq 35\%$) is related to first-order phase transition behavior,³⁻⁶ which gradually shifts to a second-order transition with more pronounced relaxor character at higher TrFE contents.^{8,9} The melting temperature of the copolymers increases linearly with increasing TrFE content, i.e., from 151 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 30TrFE to 162 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 55TrFE (Figs. S4c and S5a). The same linear trend is observed for the crystallization temperature, which consistently occurs about 18 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ lower than the melting point (Figs. S4f and S5a). These results are in good agreement with previous reports.^{6,10}

Comparison of the enthalpies (ΔH) of the ferroelectric to paraelectric phase transitions shows a decreasing trend with increasing TrFE content, from ~ 20 J g^{-1} in 30TrFE to ~ 3 J g^{-1} in 55TrFE (Fig. S5b). This indicates that the shift of T_C to lower temperatures promoted by TrFE is also accompanied by a decrease in the latent heat of the ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition. These results are consistent with the fact that higher TrFE content causes the ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition to shift from first to second order, eventually leading to reduced ferroelectricity in TrFE-rich ($>50\%$) compositions. This reduction has been linked to the instability of the ferroelectric all-trans conformation when a larger amount of TrFE units is present.^{5,9} The addition of TrFE co-monomer also affects the melting enthalpy, with a slight linear decrease from ~ 29 J g^{-1} in 30TrFE to ~ 26 J g^{-1} in 55TrFE observed (Fig. S5b), which could be related to slightly lower crystallinity.⁹

Figure S4. Temperature dependence of the DSC signal of (a-c) second heating and (d-f) second cooling of 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30-0.55$) copolymer powders, with an enlarged view of the temperature ranges in which (b, e) ferroelectric-paraelectric (Curie temperature), (c) melting and (f) crystallization transitions occur.

Figure S5. (a) Temperatures and (b) enthalpies of Curie temperature (T_C on heating and cooling), melting point and crystallization as a function of TrFE content in 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30-0.55$) copolymer powders obtained from DSC measurements. The variation of T_C in TrFE-poor ($x < 0.45$) compositions corresponds to the position of the first and last peak in the corresponding DSC curves.

The temperature dependence of the DSC signals for 32TrFE-8CFE, 31TrFE-7CFE and 28TrFE-7CTFE terpolymer powders from the second heating and cooling run is shown in Fig. S6. For both the 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymers, aside from melting, no pronounced endothermic peak is observed during heating over the entire measured temperature range, confirming the relaxor ferroelectric nature of both compositions (Fig. S6b).¹¹⁻¹⁴ However, a small kink at ~ 10 °C may indicate a structural transformation,^{12,14} but this cannot be sufficiently confirmed due to its proximity to the starting measurement temperature and the potentially larger associated measurement error. In contrast to ceramic perovskite relaxor materials,^{15,16} PVDF-based terpolymers have been shown to undergo a continuous structural phase transition even from the relaxor to the paraelectric phase.^{12,17,18} In the absence of detectable peaks related to the ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition, it is confirmed that 7–8% CFE ter-monomer is sufficient to completely convert 35TrFE copolymer (base composition, considering the actual VDF and TrFE ratio) from ferroelectric to relaxor-like behavior. An additional peak at ~ 82 °C upon cooling in 8CFE could be related to a residue of the base copolymer composition (35TrFE), as indicated by additional low-intensity melting and crystallization peaks (Fig. S6c and f). On the other hand, the 7CTFE composition shows multiple peaks upon heating (Fig. S6b) and cooling (Fig. S6e), indicating more pronounced structural phase transitions.¹⁷⁻²⁰ The presence of multiple peaks may be related to sample heterogeneity, in which multiple ferroelectric and relaxor conformations are present.^{12,13} It appears that 7% of the CTFE ter-monomer is not sufficient to completely diminish the long-range ferroelectric order in the 30TrFE copolymer (base composition), resulting in the coexistence of ferroelectric and relaxor phases. The addition of a third monomer to TrFE-based copolymers lowers the melting point, which reaches ~ 130 °C for both 8CFE and 7CFE and ~ 140 °C for 7CTFE (Figs. S6c and S7a). The presence of multiple melting peaks over a wider temperature range further supports the coexistence of multiple structural and/or chemical conformations.¹²

Since all terpolymer compositions exhibit pronounced relaxor-like behavior, this strongly influences the enthalpy of the associated structural ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transitions (Fig. S7b). Accordingly, both CFE-based compositions show zero latent heat, while the latent heat of the (relaxor)ferroelectric-to-paraelectric phase transition in 7CTFE is ~ 4 J g⁻¹, which is within the range of copolymers with 50% TrFE (Fig. S5b). The addition of bulky CFE and CTFE ter-monomers also affects the melting enthalpy, which is directly related to the degree of crystallinity of the polymers.^{12,19} Compared to the copolymers, all terpolymers have lower melting enthalpies and thus a lower degree of crystallinity (Figs. S5b and S7b). 7CFE has the highest melting enthalpy at ~ 22.4 J g⁻¹, while it decreases by $\sim 17\%$ (to ~ 18.7 J g⁻¹) for 8CFE, suggesting that a higher amount ($\geq 8\%$) of CFE ter-monomer has a detrimental effect on the degree of crystallinity. Therefore, a lower amount of CFE ter-monomer ($< 8\%$) is preferable for electrocaloric applications. The slightly bulkier CTFE ter-monomer results in a melting enthalpy similar to that of 8CFE (i.e., 19.2 J g⁻¹ in 7CTFE), but unlike the CFE counterpart, this amount is still insufficient to fully convert a ferroelectric into a relaxor-like material.¹¹ It should be noted that CFE- or CTFE-based terpolymers represent a complex system in which many competing factors such as the degree of crystallinity, the amounts of ferroelectric and relaxor phases, the ratios between different monomers and the presence of different

compositional conformations influence the functional properties of the material, making comparison with reported studies difficult.

Figure S6. Temperature dependence of the DSC signal of (a-c) second heating and (d-f) second cooling of 8CFE, 7CFE and 7CTFE powders, with an enlarged view of the temperature ranges in which (b, e) (relaxor)ferroelectric-paraelectric, (c) melting and (f) crystallization transitions occur.

Figure S7. (a) Temperatures and (b) enthalpies of phase transitions (T_m on heating and cooling), melting point and crystallization of 8CFE, 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymer powders obtained from DSC measurements.

S4.) Dielectric spectroscopy of films

The temperature and frequency dependence of ϵ_r' and $\tan\delta$ on cooling for all 100xTrFE-based copolymers ($x = 0.30\text{--}0.55$) and the 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymer films are shown in Fig. S8a and b, respectively. In contrast to the heating curves, where the T_C of the copolymers clearly shifts to lower temperatures with increasing TrFE co-monomer content (Fig. 1a in the manuscript), the cooling curves show significant temperature stability of T_C , which is almost independent of TrFE content (Fig. S8a). For all copolymers, T_C decreases on cooling by only ~ 8 °C as TrFE comonomer content increases, from ~ 74 °C for 30TrFE to ~ 66 °C for the 55TrFE composition (both measured at 1 kHz). This large discrepancy between heating and cooling runs results from substantial thermal hysteresis in TrFE-poor ($\leq 35\%$) compositions, which is related to a first-order ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition.^{4-6,9} The same trend was also observed in the DSC analysis (Section S3), confirming that this behavior is indeed related to structural phase transitions of the materials. It should be noted that slight deviations in the results were obtained due to the different dynamics of DSC measurements compared to dielectric measurements. Additionally, the different degrees of crystallinity and mobility of the polymer chains in powders and solution-based films could also influence the characterization results.³

For the terpolymers, the 7CFE composition shows almost identical permittivity results during cooling and heating, with the only difference being a local maximum observed on heating, likely due to compositional heterogeneity (see Fig. 1a in the manuscript).^{19,21} In contrast, the 7CTFE composition exhibits a small thermal hysteresis of ~ 4 °C, with a peak-permittivity at ~ 50 °C on heating and ~ 46 °C on cooling, indicating the coexistence of ferroelectric and relaxor-like phases.^{12,13} These results are in good agreement with the relaxor-ferroelectric nature of both compositions and can be directly related to the DSC analysis results (Section S3).

Figure S8. Temperature dependence of (a) ϵ' at different frequencies and (b) $\tan\delta$ at 1 kHz during cooling of 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30-0.55$) copolymer, 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymer films.

Electric field-dependent permittivity measurements were performed to investigate the stability of thermal hysteresis associated with a first-order ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition, observed as a large asymmetry between heating and cooling in TrFE-poor ($\leq 35\%$) compositions. Unlike the previously presented permittivity measurements obtained at zero DC bias field (Figs. 1a in the manuscript and S8), different DC voltage signals of $\pm 200\text{--}800\text{ V}$ (i.e., $\sim 25\text{--}100\text{ V }\mu\text{m}^{-1}$) were applied (Fig. S9a and b), while the AC voltage signal of 0.15 V remained unchanged. Measurements were performed on unpoled samples during heating and cooling runs between $5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $140\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with temperature stabilization steps every $1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, at 1 kHz . Each measurement point used to generate the temperature- and field-dependent ϵ_r' data shown in Fig. S9c and d was obtained at zero field after exposure to a defined variation of the DC bias field (i.e., $\sim 25\text{--}100\text{ V }\mu\text{m}^{-1}$).

Since the largest asymmetry between heating and cooling of $\sim 36\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was obtained at 30TrFE, this composition was chosen to investigate how the applied external electric field affects the stability of the ferroelectric/paraelectric phase and the associated thermal hysteresis. As expected, an external electric field favors stabilization of the ferroelectric phase, leading to a decrease in thermal hysteresis (Fig. S9e and f). While the T_C obtained during heating is largely independent of the applied bias field, the T_C during cooling increases with increasing electric field. The thermal hysteresis, shown as the difference between the T_C during heating and the T_C during cooling, decreases almost linearly from $\sim 36\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $\sim 6\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as the electric field increases from 0 to $\sim 75\text{ V }\mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (Fig. S9f). Thermal hysteresis saturates when higher electric fields are applied, resulting in a ΔT of $\sim 5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ after application of $100\text{ V }\mu\text{m}^{-1}$. These results indicate that the paraelectric phase in TrFE-poor ($\leq 35\%$) copolymer compositions becomes quite stable once the paraelectric-ferroelectric phase transition is exceeded, which could pose a problem for use in some applications. However, to trigger a reasonably large electrocaloric effect in copolymers, electric fields of at least $100\text{ V }\mu\text{m}^{-1}$ are typically required, at which point the thermal hysteresis is already significantly reduced.

Figure S9. Electric field-dependent (a) ϵ_r' and (b) $\tan\delta$ loops at 25°C and 1 kHz ; temperature dependence of ϵ_r' at 1 kHz during (c) heating and (d) cooling of the 30TrFE copolymer film.

Each point represents a value obtained at zero field after exposure to a defined variation of the DC bias field up to $\pm 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. (e) Extracted T_C values during heating and cooling and (f) their difference determined from temperature-dependent ϵ_r' measurements.

S5.) Room-temperature bipolar polarization–electric field loops

Room temperature j – E and corresponding P – E hysteresis loops of 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30$ – 0.55) copolymers are shown in Figs. S10 and S11, respectively. The bipolar loops were measured at 1 Hz and at different electric fields up to $\sim 140 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, with steps of $\sim 10 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. Comparison of the j – E hysteresis loops of the copolymers shows a clear change in the switching current peaks, which become broader and less pronounced as TrFE content increases (Fig. S10). This abrupt transition is related to the transformation of the ferroelectric from a first-order phase transition to a second-order-like phase transition with more pronounced relaxor behavior, and to the further decrease in ferroelectricity with increasing TrFE content. This behavior is also reflected in the P – E hysteresis loops, where a decreasing trend of P_{max} , P_{r} and E_{C} is observed with increasing TrFE content (Fig. S11).

Room temperature j – E and P – E hysteresis loops of 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers, measured up to $\sim 110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (in $\sim 10 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ step) show pronounced relaxor behavior, as indicated by double switching current peaks and slimmer, tilted P – E loops with relatively low P_{r} and E_{C} , while maintaining relatively large P_{max} values (Fig. S12). The difference in size and dipole moment between the CFE and CTFE ter-monomers strongly affects the ferroelectric properties,^{20,22} resulting in $\sim 25\%$ larger P_{max} values in 7CFE compared to 7CTFE, while P_{r} and E_{C} are almost identical (Fig. S12a and b). Furthermore, the distinct properties of the two ter-monomers are also reflected in the shape of the hysteresis, leading to more double-like or pinched loops in 7CFE and more ferroelectric-like hysteresis loops in the 7CTFE composition. The presence of pinching is clearly recognized by the appearance of double current peaks in the j – E loops (Fig. S12c).

Figure S10. Bipolar j – E hysteresis loops of 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30$ – 0.55) copolymers at 25 °C, 1 Hz and different electric fields up to $\sim 140 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. Note the difference in the scale of j .

Figure S11. Bipolar P - E hysteresis loops of 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30$ – 0.55) copolymers at 25 °C, 1 Hz and different electric fields up to $140 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

Figure S12. Bipolar (a, b) P - E and (c, d) j - E hysteresis loops of 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers at 25 °C, 1 Hz and different electric fields up to $110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

S6.) Temperature dependent polarization data

Unipolar P - E hysteresis loops of 35TrFE, 45TrFE and 50TrFE copolymer films were measured over a temperature range of 10–100 °C in 5 °C increments, using a triangular waveform at 100 Hz and electric fields up to $\sim 140 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. Each sample was pre-poled with several bipolar cycles up to the maximum applied measurement field before measurements. Examples of measured P - E loops at $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ with a temperature interval of 10 °C are shown in Fig. S13. The P - E loops were used to construct the $P(E,T)$ curves shown in Fig. S14, where each data point represents the maximum value from a separately measured unipolar P - E loop.

The comparison of the peak P_{max} values for all three copolymer compositions in Fig. S14 at low fields ($< 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$) aligns well with the T_{C} values obtained from low-field permittivity measurements (Fig. 1a in the manuscript). The maximum P_{max} values for 35TrFE, 45TrFE and 50TrFE at $\sim 140 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ were observed at 95 °C ($\sim 7.8 \text{ } \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$), 70 °C ($\sim 6.4 \text{ } \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) and 55 °C ($\sim 4.8 \text{ } \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$), respectively (Fig. S14). Note that increased electrical conductivity at higher temperatures ($> 80 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$), evident from the largely open hysteresis loop in Fig. S13, could affect the P_{max} values and result in a slight overestimation. Accordingly, a general trend is observed: the P_{max} value increases near T_{C} , and the P_{max} value at room temperature decreases as TrFE content decreases. These results are consistent with the increasing first-order character of the ferroelectric phase transition in the samples as TrFE content decreases, as already indicated by the dielectric permittivity, DSC and bipolar P - E hysteresis loop measurements.

Figure S13. Temperature-dependent unipolar P - E hysteresis loops of (a) 35TrFE, (b) 45TrFE and (c) 50TrFE copolymers measured at $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (left) and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (right) at 100 Hz.

Figure S14. Temperature- and field-dependent P_{\max} of (a) 35TrFE, (b) 45TrFE and (c) 50TrFE copolymers determined from unipolar P - E loops measured at 100 Hz.

Similar to copolymers, the unipolar P - E hysteresis loops of 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymer films were measured under the same conditions with electric fields up to $\sim 110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. Examples of measured P - E loops at $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ with a temperature step of 10°C are shown in Fig. S15. $P(E, T)$ data obtained from the peak values of separately measured unipolar P - E loops are shown in Fig. S16. No clear, well-defined peak was observed in the $P(E, T)$ curves over the entire temperature range, consistent with the relaxor character of the terpolymers. However, a slight increase in 7CFE at higher fields ($>90 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$) may indicate a

field-induced relaxor-to-ferroelectric phase transition responsible for the appearance of double-like hysteresis loops previously observed in the bipolar P - E loops at room temperature (Fig. S12). 7CFE reaches a maximum P_{\max} value of $\sim 5.7 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ at 50°C , while 7CTFE exhibits a $\sim 23\%$ lower P_{\max} value of $\sim 4.4 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ at 35°C , both at $\sim 110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (Fig. S16).

Figure S15. Temperature-dependent unipolar P - E hysteresis loops of (a) 7CFE and (b) 7CTFE terpolymers measured at $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (left) and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (right) at 100 Hz.

Figure S16. Temperature- and field-dependent P_{\max} of (a) 7CFE and (b) 7CTFE terpolymers determined from unipolar P - E loops measured at 100 Hz.

S7.) Comparison of 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymers

To determine whether increasing the CFE ter-monomer content in the 31TrFE-7CFE composition could further enhance relaxor behavior and possibly shift the permittivity peak, resulting in an enhanced EC effect at even lower temperatures, two terpolymer compositions with similar TrFE content and varying CFE ter-monomer levels were investigated. Comparison of the temperature dependence of ϵ_r' and $\tan\delta$ during heating and cooling for the 31TrFE-7CFE and 32TrFE-8CFE compositions in Fig. S17 shows that adding 8% CFE has only a minimal effect on shifting the peak permittivity temperature further to lower values, $\sim 26^\circ\text{C}$ instead of $\sim 28^\circ\text{C}$ in the 7CFE composition. However, it has a detrimental effect on the dielectric response, resulting in $\sim 11\%$ lower peak permittivity value of ~ 49 in 8CFE compared to ~ 55 in 7CFE (both at 1 kHz), which is likely related to the excessive amount of the bulky CFE ter-monomer in the base TrFE-based ferroelectric conformation, resulting in a lower degree of crystallinity (Section S3). In contrast, $\tan\delta$ remains comparable in both compositions over the entire temperature range at 1 kHz (Fig. 17b).

Figure S17. Temperature dependence of (a) ϵ_r' and (b) $\tan\delta$ at 1 kHz during heating and cooling of 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymer films.

A lower degree of crystallinity and excessively disrupted long-range ferroelectric order are also reflected in a weakened macroscopic ferroelectric response, resulting in $\sim 15\%$ lower P_{\max} values in 8CFE compared to 7CFE, as shown by room-temperature bipolar and temperature-dependent unipolar P - E loops (Figs. S18 and S19).

Figure S18. Bipolar P - E hysteresis loops of 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymers at 25 °C, 1 Hz and various electric fields up to $110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

Figure S19. (a) Unipolar P - E hysteresis loops of 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymers at 25 °C, 100 Hz and various electric fields up to $\sim 120 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and (b) temperature dependence of P_{\max} determined from unipolar P - E loops measured at 100 Hz, $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

Most importantly, the reduced dielectric and polarization response in the 8CFE composition results in a significantly lower EC cooling effect, leading to ~30% lower EC-induced ΔT over the entire measured temperature range at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (Fig. S20). These results confirm that incorporating 7% CFE ter-monomer into the 35TrFE base copolymer provides a good compromise between sufficient relaxor-ferroelectric behavior with peak permittivity near room temperature, and maintaining a sufficiently high level of crystallinity. More details about the direct electrocaloric measurements used are provided in Section 8, Materials and Methods and in our previous work.²

Figure S20. Temperature dependence of EC-induced ΔT for EC cooling of 7CFE and 8CFE terpolymers at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

S8.) Direct electrocaloric measurements with infrared camera

Direct EC measurements with an IR camera typically require an additional coating to increase the emissivity of the measured surface. For accurate temperature readings with minimized measurement error, the emissivity should remain above 0.6 across the entire measured temperature range, ensuring that most of the emitted energy detected by the IR camera originates from the sample's thermal radiation. If the emissivity of an opaque material is low (i.e., < 0.5), surface reflectivity dominates, and the IR camera primarily detects reflected radiation from the surroundings, resulting in incorrect temperature readings. For example, in the IR thermogram shown in Fig. S21b, although the stage is set to ~ 40 °C, most of the top Au electrode appears to be at ~ 28 °C (the laboratory's ambient temperature) or even below 0 °C (due to partial reflection of the cooled detector inside the IR camera). Therefore, ensuring sufficiently high emissivity is essential when selecting the most appropriate sample surface coating.

Besides emissivity, another important factor for reliable direct EC measurements is ensuring that the additional coating material adds minimal EC-inactive mass to the sample stack, allowing the capture of EC-induced ΔT as close as possible to the adiabatic limit. Minimizing the ratio between the adiabatic (ΔT_{EC}) and measured (ΔT) EC effect, defined as the correction factor (k),² results in more reliable and trustworthy measurements with lower uncertainty and less opportunity for manipulation. Therefore, minimizing the amount of required high-emissivity coating is especially important when characterizing thin films with small active areas.

To achieve a good balance between sufficiently high emissivity and minimizing the correction factor, two black ink coatings of different thicknesses were used in this work (Fig. S21a). Thick black ink dots (black matte spray) were applied to the EC-inactive part of the sample (away from the active, electroded part), while small 3–5 μm thick black ink layers (printed with a commercial office printer) were applied to the EC-active part of the sample (top Au electrode). The thick black ink dots were used to obtain the actual base temperature of the sample at any time by assuming emissivity 1, while the measured EC-induced ΔT of the sample was determined from the printed black ink layers, whose emissivity was calculated based on the base temperature measured on the thick black ink. Carefully controlling the thickness of the printed black ink layers relative to the thickness of the EC-active polymer films ensured that the emissivity of the printed black ink layers for all studied compositions was higher than 0.6 under all measurement conditions (Fig. 21c). This is especially important for measurements at higher temperatures, where the emissivity of thin black ink layers tends to decrease as temperature increases.

To verify the determination of the base ambient temperature of the sample using the thick black ink dot, and assuming its emissivity is 1, the temperature of the heating stage was also confirmed with a small Type K thermocouple. Simultaneous measurement of the sample temperature on the heating stage with the IR camera on the thick black ink dots and a thermocouple placed below the sample showed good agreement across the entire measured temperature range, 15–100 °C (Fig. S21d and e). The difference between the two measured absolute temperatures was in the range of (0.5 ± 0.2) °C, indicating that thick black ink layers

can be used to reliably determine the base temperature of the samples during the EC measurements.

Figure S21. (a) Photograph, (b) IR thermogram with marked areas for temperature readings and (c) layer thickness and temperature dependence of emissivity for selected copolymer and terpolymer films. (d, e) Stage temperature calibration using a thermocouple and IR camera.

The temperature profiles for typical EC cycles, consisting of adiabatic polarization (heating peak) and adiabatic depolarization (cooling peak), measured with an IR camera on the printed black ink layers, are shown in Fig. S22. In Fig. S22, temporal profiles for a few selected ambient temperatures and the maximum applied electric field for 45TrFE copolymer, 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers are displayed, while complete temperature- and electric field-dependent ΔT measurements, averaging multiple EC heating and EC cooling peaks for all examined copolymers and terpolymers, are shown in Figs. S23 and S24, respectively.

Figure S22. Sequence of three EC cycles measured with an IR camera at different ambient temperatures and electric fields for (a) 45TrFE, (b) 7CFE and (c) 7CTFE films.

Figure S23. Temperature- and electric field-dependent ΔT measured with an IR camera for EC heating (left) and EC cooling (right) effects of (a) 35TrFE, (b) 45TrFE and (c) 50TrFE copolymers.

Figure S24. Temperature- and electric field-dependent ΔT measured with an IR camera for EC heating (left) and EC cooling (right) effects of (a) 7CFE and (b) 7CTFE terpolymers.

To assess the reproducibility of the selected EC measurement method and verify the quality of the prepared samples and their processing, the EC effect of several different samples for each composition was compared. Electric-field-dependent ΔT measurements of 3–5 copolymers and terpolymers at temperatures corresponding to their peak EC cooling effect values and at ~ 30 °C are shown in Figs. S25 and S26, respectively. Despite slight variations in film and black ink layer thicknesses among the samples, the EC responses of multiple samples show comparable results for all studied compositions.

Figure S25. Electric field-dependent ΔT cooling effects of multiple (a) 35TrFE, (b) 45TrFE and (c) 50TrFE copolymers, measured at temperatures corresponding to the peak values (top) and at 30 °C (bottom).

Figure S26. Electric field-dependent ΔT cooling effects of multiple (a) 7CFE and (b) 7CTFE terpolymers, measured at temperatures corresponding to the peak values (top) and at 30 °C (bottom).

To demonstrate the importance of accurate emissivity determination and how insufficient or inaccurate emissivity affects direct EC measurements with an IR camera, a hypothetical experiment was conducted on one of the experimentally measured EC cycles. An example of a measured EC cycle for 7CFE terpolymer at ~ 39 °C and ~ 100 V μm^{-1} is shown in Fig. S27a, where EC heating and cooling effects were obtained after our standard emissivity determination process described above (Fig. S21). Matching the base temperature of the printed black ink layer on the sample (green curve in Fig. S27a) with the temperature of the thick black ink dots (black curve in Fig. S27a) resulted in a corrected emissivity of 0.77, which was also used to obtain the results in Fig. S24a.

Using 0.77 as the correct emissivity, several hypothetical examples with overestimated and underestimated emissivity values were selected to demonstrate how the chosen emissivity affects the measured absolute temperature and, most importantly, the induced ΔT used to determine the EC effect. In all cases, a base temperature of 39 °C and an EC-induced ΔT cooling effect of ~ 3.8 K obtained at an emissivity of 0.77 were used as references for comparison. If the emissivity of the sample is overestimated, for example, assumed to be 1 instead of 0.77 (see blue curve in Fig. S27b), this results in a slightly lower determined baseline temperature of 36 °C compared to the actual sample stage temperature of 39 °C, and $\sim 18\%$ lower ΔT of EC cooling, namely ~ 3.1 K instead of ~ 3.8 K at ~ 100 V μm^{-1} (Fig. S27d). Conversely, underestimating the sample emissivity has the opposite effect, causing the base temperature to appear much higher than the actual value, i.e., 47 °C and 63 °C when considering surface emissivity of 0.5 and 0.25, respectively (see orange and red curves in Fig. S27b). Most critically, underestimating surface emissivity not only largely overestimates the measured absolute temperature of the sample, but also leads to a significant overestimation of the EC-induced ΔT , namely $\sim 30\%$ higher ΔT cooling effect of ~ 4.9 K for an emissivity of 0.5 and more than 80% higher ΔT cooling effect of ~ 6.9 K when considering an emissivity of 0.25 (both at ~ 100 V μm^{-1} , Fig. S27d).

Since, for an opaque material, a change in emissivity is inversely proportional to a change in reflectivity, underestimating the surface emissivity reduces the contribution of the sample's thermal radiation and consequently overcompensates for the contribution of reflected radiation from the surroundings. This results in incorrect absolute temperature measurements and exaggerated temperature changes. This experiment underscores the importance of using the correct and sufficiently high emissivity for direct EC measurements with an IR camera, as errors in emissivity can cause large errors in the measured EC effect (Section S12). Therefore, when using an IR camera, it is essential to ensure that the base temperature always matches the actual ambient temperature and to always present the raw data to avoid misleading results, which is often not the case in studies reported in literature.

Figure S27. EC cycles of 7CFE terpolymer film measured with an IR camera at 39°C and $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ with surface emissivity of (a) 0.77 and (b) ranging from 0.25 to 1. Electric field dependent (c) EC heating and (d) EC cooling ΔT as a function of selected surface emissivity.

S9.) Specific heat capacity of polymer powders

The specific heat capacity (c_p) of active polymer materials is needed for finite element modeling, calculation of the correction factor for direct EC characterization (Section S10) and for indirect characterization of the EC effect (Section S11). The temperature dependence of c_p for all studied copolymer and terpolymer compositions was determined using the same DSC measurement data presented in Section 3. In addition to DSC measurements of polymer powders, the same thermal treatment, i.e., two consecutive heating and cooling cycles between 0 °C and 180 °C, at heating and cooling rates of 5 K min⁻¹, was performed on a sapphire disk-shaped standard sample. The $c_p(T)$ values shown in Fig. S28 and Table S1 were determined from the second heating DSC run, using the known c_p values of the standard material.²³

Figure S28. (a) Temperature dependence of c_p for various copolymer and terpolymer powders in the range 0–100 °C, (b) enlarged view of the data from 0–50 °C and (c) comparison of selected c_p values measured at 0 °C, 25 °C and 50 °C.

Table S1. Collected c_p data for various copolymer and terpolymer compositions at different temperatures.

T [°C]	c_p [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]							
	30TrFE	35TrFE	45TrFE	50TrFE	55TrFE	31TrFE-7CFE	32TrFE-8CFE	28TrFE-7CTFE
0	1068	1121	1099	1065	1067	1176	1179	1099
10	1095	1161	1139	1089	1094	1251	1252	1145
20	1134	1207	1186	1136	1139	1262	1265	1183*
25	1154	1232	1213	1162	1165	1263	1269	1199*
30	1173	1254	1242	1190	1193	1259	1276	1213*
40	1214	1307	1292*	1232*	1226*	1265	1291	1246*
50	1257	1373	1338*	1276*	1258*	1277	1312	1275*
60	1306*	1418*	1380*	1323*	1288*	1288	1334	1306*
70	1352*	1469*	1423*	1364*	1323*	1299*	1355*	1319
80	1398*	1521*	1464*	1410*	1355*	1306*	1374*	1334
90	1453*	1568*	1502*	1452*	1385*	1312*	1393*	1351*
100	1497*	1615	1539	1497	1417*	1319*	1414*	1357*

* derived from the baseline

S10.) Finite element modeling

A 2D finite element model was used to determine how much EC-induced heat generated in the active polymer films is dissipated to the surroundings before being detected by an IR camera. This was assessed through a time-dependent heat transfer study of the EC-active polymer layer and the subsequent heat dissipation to the surrounding EC-inactive parts (mainly the black ink layer) of a sample stack. The model used the exact dimensions and physical properties of the sample stacks from the experiments (Fig. S29). The intrinsic or adiabatic EC effect of an active polymer film was then obtained by fitting the model to the experimental data (Fig. S30a). More details of the method are available in our previous work.^{2,28}

As a result, the ratio of the adiabatic EC effect of the polymer film obtained from the numerical model ($\Delta T_{\text{ad.}}$) to the experimentally measured EC-induced temperature change on top of the printed black ink layer ($\Delta T_{\text{meas.}}$) was used to calculate the correction factor (k) for selected compositions and temperatures, which was then used to construct Fig. 4 in the manuscript. The obtained k values of ~ 1.15 , ~ 1.20 and ~ 1.10 for the selected 45TrFE, 7CFE and 7CTFE compositions, respectively, indicate that about 10–20% of the EC-induced heat is dissipated before being detected by the IR camera (Fig. S30b). The k values show a weak temperature dependence (Fig. S30b and d) and correlate well with the measured thickness ratio between the polymer films and printed black ink layers (Fig. S21c).

Given that the EC-induced heat (Q) is instantaneously dissipated throughout all parts of a sample stack, the ratio of the heat capacities (C_p) of the active polymer film to the surrounding EC-inactive layers provides a faster alternative to finite element modeling for determining the adiabatic EC effect (Fig. S30c). Approximating the black ink layer as the only EC-inactive component and considering only the portion of the polymer film beneath the black ink layer as the EC-active part provides a good estimate of k , deviating by no more than 3% compared to the modeling (Fig. S30d). The results align well with numerical calculations because the EC effect occurs so rapidly that thermal conductivity does not significantly influence the peak in measured ΔT , making the method more accessible and generally applicable for direct characterization of the EC effect.

(b) Table summarizing the structural and thermal parameters of all components included in the numerical model.

Component	d [μm]	ρ [kg m^{-3}]	c_p [$\text{J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]				λ [$\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$]
Au electrode	0.15	19300 *	129 ^[24]				318 ^[25]
black ink	on 45TrFE	3.3	710 ^[26]				0.3 ^[26]
	on 7CFE	4.9					
	on 7CTFE	3.5					
polymer layer	45TrFE	1880 **	1242 (30 °C)	1359 (55 °C)	1464 (80 °C)	1502 (90 °C)	0.21 ^[27]
	7CFE	1780 **	1262 (20 °C)	1259 (30 °C)	1265 (40 °C)	1277 (50 °C)	
	7CTFE	13.4	1183 (20 °C)	1246 (40 °C)	1275 (50 °C)		

* theoretical bulk density ** measured at 25 °C

Figure S29. (a) Schematic representation of the layout and dimensions of the entire sample stack used for the EC measurement, with (b) a table summarizing the structural and thermal parameters of all components included in the numerical model.

(b)

Sample	$T [^{\circ}\text{C}]$	$E [\text{V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}]$	$\Delta T_{\text{meas.}} [\text{K}]$	$\Delta T_{\text{ad.}} [\text{K}]$	k
45TrFE	29.9	141	1.55	1.78	1.150
	53.8		2.85	3.25	1.140
	77.9		5.67	6.43	1.134
	92.0		4.67	6.07	1.130
7CFE	19.8	114	2.63	3.17	1.204
	29.4		3.43	4.13	1.203
	38.7		4.31	5.17	1.200
	48.3		3.73	4.47	1.198
7CTFE	20.2	97	1.35	1.49	1.103
	39.9		3.02	3.33	1.102
	54.4		3.94	4.33	1.100

(c) C_p ratio calculation

$0.5 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$

$d_{\text{b,ink}}$

d_{polymer}

$$Q_{\text{p.film}} = Q_{\text{p.film+b.ink}} = m \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T$$

$$k = \frac{\Delta T_{\text{ad.}}}{\Delta T_{\text{meas.}}}$$

$$k = \frac{m_{\text{p.film}} \cdot c_{\text{p, p.film}} + m_{\text{b.ink}} \cdot c_{\text{p, b.ink}}}{m_{\text{p.film}} \cdot c_{\text{p, p.film}}}$$

Figure S30. (a) Experimentally measured ΔT of EC-induced heating at various ambient temperatures and (b) temperature dependence of the correction factors (k) for 45TrFE, 7CFE and 7CTFE compositions determined by a numerical model. (c) Calculation of k from C_p -ratio calculations and (d) comparison with k obtained from modeling.

S11.) Indirect electrocaloric measurements – Landau phenomenological approach

The indirect estimation of the EC effect was conducted using a simplified Landau phenomenological model, as described in Eq. 1 (Materials and Methods section). P_r and P_{max} values (Figs. S14 and S16) were obtained from the temperature-dependent unipolar P – E loops (Figs. S13 and S15), and the β coefficient was determined from ϵ_r' during heating (Fig. 1 in the manuscript). Temperature- and electric field-dependent indirectly obtained ΔT_{EC} values for all examined copolymer and terpolymer compositions are shown in Fig. S31. Peak values for each composition at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ were used for comparison in Fig. 4c of the manuscript, while temperature-dependent comparisons between indirectly and directly measured EC effects at selected fields are shown in Fig. S32.

Comparing the results of both methods shows that the Landau model provides a reasonably good approximation when considering only the peak values (not necessarily obtained at the same temperature). However, larger discrepancies arise when comparing temperature-dependent data. This is consistent with the fact that this method should, in principle, be valid only at the phase transition and also highlights a limitation of the strongly simplified model, in which only two parameters cannot reliably represent the entire temperature range. Additionally, the difference between direct and indirect measurements becomes more pronounced at higher applied electric fields (see the comparison between $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in Fig. S32), confirming that the simplified Landau phenomenological model does not adequately account for the saturation of polarization at higher fields. Consequently, estimation of the EC was restricted to only the peak values in this work (Fig. 4c in the manuscript).

Figure S31. Temperature- and electric field-dependent ΔT_{EC} of (a) 35TrFE, (b) 45TrFE, (c) 50TrFE, (d) 7CFE and (e) 7CTFE compositions obtained using the Landau indirect method.

Figure S32. Comparison of ΔT_{EC} obtained by direct measurements using an IR camera and modeling and ΔT_{EC} indirectly determined using the Landau indirect method for selected (a) copolymers and (b) terpolymers at $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (top) and $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (bottom).

S12.) Electrocaloric measurements of polymer films - comparison with the literature

Comparison of the directly obtained EC effect of TrFE-based copolymers presented in this work with reported literature data was possible only for the 45TrFE composition. EC characterization of the 50TrFE composition has not yet been addressed in the literature, and the lack of systematic studies near the peak EC values in 35TrFE prevents reliable comparison. The electric field-dependent maximum ΔT_{EC} for cooling, obtained by the IR camera and numerical modeling in this work at ~ 78 °C, along with its comparison to relevant directly measured data at peak EC values (~ 70 °C) reported in the literature, is presented in Fig. S33 and Table S2. Lines representing a logarithmic regression of selected data points are included to facilitate visual comparison of trends between different measurement methods.

To date, the EC effect of 45TrFE films has been directly characterized only with thermistors in high-resolution calorimeters, and no IR camera measurements have been performed in this temperature range. Comparing the results obtained in this work by IR camera and modeling (green stars in Fig. S33) with thermistor-in-calorimeter measurements (pink symbols in Fig. S33) reveals a large discrepancy between the two direct methods, with the thermistor method yielding, on average, values 50% and even over 100% higher than those from the IR camera measurements. The significantly larger values obtained with the thermistor method, which cannot be clearly explained due to the lack of reported experimental details and measurement data, are likely related to the use of larger correction factors required because of the longer response time of the thermistor.²

Figure S33. ΔT_{EC} peak values at different electric fields obtained by the thermistor-based direct measurement method for 45TrFE copolymers reported in the literature, compared with the results of this study. The numbering corresponds to the references in Table S2. The lines represent logarithmic regression and serve as a visual guide for comparison.

Table S2. ΔT_{EC} peak values at different electric fields obtained by the thermistor-based direct measurement method for 45TrFE copolymers reported in the literature. The numbering corresponds to the graphical representation in Fig. S33.

No.	Composition	ΔT_{EC} [K]	E [$V \mu m^{-1}$]	T [$^{\circ}C$]	Method	Comments	Ref.
1	45TrFE	3.3	50	67	thermistor	in calorimeter	[29]
		10.5	100				
		12	120				
2	45TrFE	1.7	40.6	70	thermistor	in calorimeter	[30]
		5.5	83.2				
		8	120				
3	45TrFE	3	50	67	thermistor	in calorimeter	[31]
		10	100				
		12	120				

For terpolymers, the lack of reported EC studies on CTFE-based compositions limited the comparison of different EC measurements to only CFE-based compositions. Due to their excellent room-temperature EC performance, the EC properties of CFE-based terpolymer films have been extensively studied using various direct measurement methods, such as IR camera, thermistor-in-calorimeter, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and heat flux sensors. The electric field-dependent maximum ΔT_{EC} for cooling, obtained by the IR camera and numerical modeling in this work at ~ 30 °C for 7CFE, along with its comparison to relevant directly measured data at room temperature (25–30 °C) reported in the literature for 100xCFE ($x = 0.06$ – 0.09) terpolymers, is presented in Fig. S34 and Table S3. This comparison focuses exclusively on unmodified CFE-based terpolymers (where sufficient information is provided), while composites with ceramic inclusions and double-bond-modified compositions are not included. Lines representing a logarithmic regression of selected data points in Fig. S34 are added to facilitate visual comparison of trends among different measurement methods.

Comparing the results obtained in this work by IR camera and modeling (green stars in Fig. S34) with IR camera measurements from the literature (light green symbols in Fig. S34) shows good agreement. Slight variations in reported ΔT_{EC} values may result from differences in composition, ambient temperature, IR camera frame rate, or emissivity correction. Overall, the data follow the same trend line, resulting in a ΔT_{EC} of $\sim(4 \pm 1)$ K at $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. The only report using a DSC direct EC measurement method (blue symbol in Fig. S34) aligns very well with the IR camera method. Two studies using a thermistor-in-calorimeter method at lower electric fields (pink symbols in Fig. S34) also obtained values relatively similar to the IR camera method. Although systematically higher ΔT_{EC} values using the same method in 4TrFE films and a much steeper trend line compared to the IR camera method suggest that this method yields higher EC values in the case of CFE-based terpolymers as well, the lack of data points, especially at higher electric fields, prevents drawing more concrete conclusions. On the other hand, another commonly used direct EC measurement method based on heat flux sensors shows distinctly higher ΔT_{EC} values compared to other methods across the entire electric field range (black symbols in Fig. S34), with average ΔT_{EC} of $\sim(7 \pm 1)$ K at $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and $\sim(14 \pm 3)$ K at $150 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$. In addition to significantly larger values compared to the IR camera measurements, especially at higher electric fields, where EC effects of more than 22 K are reported at $180 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, the method shows highly scattered results even at the same applied electric fields. Such differences cannot be explained by variations in sample composition or selected ambient temperature alone, suggesting that the measurement method itself may be a major source of the large discrepancies with other direct EC methods. The reason for systematically larger values measured with the heat flux method compared to other methods, often exceeding a factor of 2, remains unclear and is the main motivation to address this issue and take the necessary steps to evaluate the true intrinsic EC effect in polymers, as well as to lay the foundation for standardizing direct EC measurements. If PVDF-based polymers are found to truly exhibit an adiabatic EC effect of more than 20 K (or even above 30 K, as reported in some CFE-based composites),^{41,56,57} then polymer-based EC cooling regenerators should already outperform ceramic-based devices^{58,59} and soon be ready for use in commercial applications.

Figure S34. Room-temperature (25–30 °C) ΔT_{EC} values at different electric fields obtained by various direct measurement methods for CFE-based terpolymers reported in the literature, compared with the results of this study. The numbering corresponds to the references in Table S3. The lines represent logarithmic regression and serve as a visual guide for comparison.

Table S3. Room-temperature (25–30 °C) ΔT_{EC} values at different electric fields obtained by various direct measurement methods for CFE-based terpolymers reported in the literature. The numbering corresponds to the graphical representation in Fig. S34.

No.	Composition	ΔT_{EC} [K]	E [V μm^{-1}]	T [°C]	Method	Comments	Ref.
1	CFE*	7	100	30	heat flux	/	[32]
		14.7	150	30		/	
2	CFE* (edge-on)	9	100	30		/	[33]
		16	150	30		/	
3	6CFE	7	100	30		/	[34]
		16	150	30		/	
4	6CFE	10	100	29		/	[35]
5	7CFE	7	100	RT		/	[36]
6	7CFE	7	100	RT		/	[37]
7	7.1CFE	5.1	83	RT		bilayer structure	[38]
8	7.2CFE	7	100	30		/	[39]
		15	150	30		/	
9	7.2CFE	16	150	RT		/	[40]
10	7.2CFE	4	75	RT		/	[41]
		7	100	RT		/	
		15	150	RT		/	
		22.5	180	RT		/	
11	7.5CFE	6.7	100	RT		/	[42]
		7.5	120	RT		/	
12	7.8CFE	4	75	RT		/	[43]
		7	100	RT		/	
13	7.8CFE	5.1	100	RT		/	[44]
14	8.5CFE	5	100	RT		/	[45]
		8	150	RT		/	
15	CFE*	3.3	100	27		+ modeling	[46]
16	7.1CFE	3.7	90	RT	/	[47]	
17	7.8CFE	4.5	100	RT	Em: 0.86	[48]	
		6	130	RT			
18	7.8CFE	3	100	RT	tube structure	[49]	
		6	185	RT	Em: 0.83		
19	7.8CFE	2.2	100	RT	tube structure	[50]	
		4	150	RT	Em: 0.86		
20	7.8CFE	4.3	100	30	$k = 1.2$, Em: 0.74	[28]	
21	7.8CFE	2.5	80	RT	Em: 0.83	[51]	
		4.2	120	RT			
		5.5	160	RT			
22	8CFE	5.2	90	RT	$k = 2$, Em: 0.7	[52]	
23	8CFE	4.9	100	RT	/	[53]	
15	CFE*	4	100	27	DSC	$k = 2.4$	[46]
24	7.2CFE	3.6	70	27	thermistor	in calorimeter	[54]
25	9.2CFE	2	60	RT	thermistor	/	[55]

* unknown amount

RT – room temperature

Em – emissivity k – correction factor

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